

MODELLING THE DESIGN AND OFF-DESIGN PERFORMANCE OF A MODERN RECOVERY BOILER BASED COGENERATION UNIT

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Abstract

Paper mill traditionally employ black liquor combustion in Tomlinson recovery boilers as a means of both chemicals recovery and steam and electricity cogeneration. Starting with modest capacities of hundreds tons combusted dry solids per day (t_{DS}/day), dry solids content in combusted black liquor around 60 % wt. and modest steam parameters, recovery boilers gradually evolved into what represents the best available technology today: capacities approaching 3000 t_{DS}/day , dry solids content above 85 % wt, and steam parameters above 10 MPa and 500 °C. At the same time, additional features are employed known from conventional power plants: stepwise regenerative feedwater and combustion air preheating above 200 °C and highly efficient steam turbines with condensing pressure around or below 5 kPa (a). Special feature of BAT recovery boilers not encountered in fossil fuel fired power plants is the flue gas cooler, recovering additional heat from flue gas to feedwater preheat before deaeration. This is made possible by very low SO_x content in the flue gas that allows flue gas cooling even below 140 °C without the risk of sulphuric acid condensation and the resulting low temperature corrosion. All those features accentuate increasing interest in boosting cogenerated electric energy production in the paper mills to reduce their electricity bills.

Objective assessment of obtained power production increase when switching from old obsolete recovery boilers to new BAT boilers is crucial when deciding about the corresponding investment. We elaborated material and heat balance-based model of two large scale cogeneration unit based on 2000 t_{DS}/day recovery boilers coupled with extraction-condensing steam turbines to compare their design and off-design performance in several alternative steam demand scenarios.

Introduction

More than 70 % of total pulp production in European Union is from chemical pulping¹. Due to high amounts of chemicals spent during chemical pulping process, these should be recovered to lower the costs of the process. This occurs in recovery cycle, where black liquor produced as a waste is first concentrated from about 15 % wt. to 65 – 85 % wt. dry solids and then it is combusted in recovery boiler, where both chemical and energy recovery takes place².

The recovery boiler is the most essential and most expensive part of the kraft recovery process. It is an integral part of the steam and power balance at the mill^{2,3}. In recovery boiler the organic matter dissolved during pulping is destroyed and its energy value recovered. Recovery boiler process has several unit processes⁴:

1. Combustion of organic material in black liquor to generate steam
2. Reduction of inorganic sulphur compounds to sodium sulphide
3. Production of molten inorganic salts and dissolution of said flow to weak white liquor to produce green liquor
4. Recovery of inorganic dust from flue gas to save chemicals
5. Production of sodium fume to capture combustion residue of released sulphur compounds

First recovery boilers appeared in late 1930s^{5,6} with capacities about 100 tons of dry solids per day (t_{DS}/day) and 30 years later it reached only 500 t_{DS}/day with produced steam parameters around 4 MPa and 400 °C⁶. The maximal dry solids content in black liquor was only about 50 – 65 %. Fouling was also the problem of first recovery boilers. Due to growing the chemical pulp production over the years there was a need to increase capacity of recovery boilers and improve their shortcomings⁷. In 1960, they started to install economizers in recovery boilers. Also, the concentration of black liquor was improved. First high dry solids units started coming on line in 1980's when extensive tests of effect of increasing dry solids content from 72 % to 84 % were run at several recovery boilers. They noticed, that above 75 % dry solids the SO_2 and H_2S emissions were practically zero⁴. As long as recovery boilers existed, air system development has been continuing. Over the years there have been several generations of air systems. Currently the new air systems have achieved low NO_x , but are still working on with lowering fouling⁴. Since 2004 first XXL recovery boilers have operated, when the first XXL size recovery boiler started up in China⁷. Modern XXL recovery boilers have capacities up to 10,000 t_{DS}/day with steam parameters

up to 11 MPa and 510 °C. Modern recovery boilers have large furnaces, modern air systems and high black liquor dry solids. These recovery boilers have very low flue gas emissions and SO₂ and TRS (total reduced sulphur compounds) are typically at level of zero⁷.

The aim of this work is to compare two recovery boilers – the old one with produced steam parameters 4 MPa and 400 °C and one representing the best available technology (BAT) with steam parameters 10 MPa and 500 °C. For both systems different steam demand scenarios will be considered and the electric energy production will be compared. Based on the price of recovery boilers, the incremental simple payback period will be calculated.

System description

Technology with old recovery boiler type (Figure 1) includes:

- 65 % thermal efficiency of steam production in recovery boiler
- Dry solids (DS) content in black liquor 75 % wt. with lower heating value 13.1 MJ/kg
- Parameters of very high pressure (VHP) steam produced in recovery boiler of 4 MPa (a) and 400 °C
- Direct steam use for sootblowing in amount of 8 % of produced VHP steam
- Air preheating by LP steam to 150 °C
- Extraction-condensing steam turbine – extractions at 1.2 MPa (a) and 0.6 MPa (a); condensing pressure 10 kPa (a); isentropic expansion efficiency 80 %; mechanic efficiency 95 %
- Deaerator working at 145 °C; temperature of fresh water entering the deaerator is 75 °C

In both systems (with old recovery boiler type and with modern recovery boiler) the consumption of combustion air in recovery boiler represents 4 t/t_{DS} and condensate return from paper mill represents 70 % of steam exported to the paper mill.

Figure 1. Schematic description of system with old recovery boiler type

The BAT recovery boiler technology (Figure 2) includes a modern recovery boiler with enhanced heat recuperation from flue gas, with enhanced regenerative heating of boiler feedwater (BFW) and combustion air, producing very high-quality steam. In accordance with this, following boiler parameters were considered:

- Liquor concentration from 75 % to 85 % wt. solids performed in high DS evaporator (HDS) consuming 1.2 MPa steam from steam turbine
- 75 % thermal efficiency of steam production in recovery boiler
- Parameters of very high pressure (VHP) steam produced in recovery boiler of 10 MPa (a) and 500 °C
- Air preheating stepwise by low-pressure (LP), intermediate-pressure (IP) and high-pressure (HP) steam to final temperature of 210 °C
- Direct HP steam use for sootblowing in amount of 8 % of produced VHP steam
- Extraction-condensing steam turbine – extractions at 2.3 MPa (a), 1.2 MPa (a) and 0.6 MPa (a); condensing pressure 5 kPa (a); isentropic expansion efficiency 80 %; mechanic efficiency 95 %

Table I
Parameters of eq. 1 for normal steam demand

Parameters	System with old recovery boiler type	System with modern recovery boiler
a [MW]	6.959	-0.178
$b \times 10^2$ [MW day t^{-1}]	1.238	1.578
$c \times 10^3$ [MW day t^{-1}]	5.434	8.147
$d \times 10^3$ [MW day t^{-1}]	3.586	6.424
$e \times 10^3$ [MW day t^{-1}]	0	4.767
x [t day $^{-1}$]	1410.48	1161.17

The amount of produced electric energy (EE) is shown in Figure 3. As it is shown, EE production in the system with old recovery boiler type is about 15 to 33 MW with increasing amount of combusted black liquor. In the system with modern recovery boiler the EE production is about 30 to 62 MW. This means that EE production in the system with modern recovery boiler is almost 2 times higher than in the system with old recovery boiler type. Efficiency of EE production in Figure 3 is calculated as the ratio of the amount of EE generated in the turbine P_{el} and amount of energy contained in the black liquor Q_{BL} :

$$\eta_{el} = \frac{P_{el}}{Q_{BL}} \tag{2}$$

Figure 3. Efficiency of EE production from the steam (left) and amount of produced EE (right) with different black liquor DS inlet and different steam demands

According to data in the literature, the price of modern recovery boiler with capacity of 2000 t_{DS}/day is about 130 mil. €. The assumed investment cost of old recovery boiler type is about 60 % of modern recovery boiler price. With the current average EE price of 34 €/MWh, the simple incremental payback period is about 9 years. Simple incremental payback period for different prices of EE is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Simple incremental payback period of modern recovery boiler purchase compared to the old type recovery boiler for different prices of EE

Conclusion

As we supposed, the efficiency of steam turbine decreases with the decreasing amount of combusted black liquor, as the nominal load of steam to turbine is the amount of steam produced from the combustion of 2000 t_{DS} /day black liquor.

Due to higher efficiency of modern recovery boiler and higher pressure and temperature of produced steam the efficiency of EE production in the system with modern recovery boiler is about 2 times higher than the efficiency of the system with old recovery boiler type. As it is shown in Figure 4 the simple incremental payback period can vary between 3 to 10 years.

Current development of recovery boilers with higher thermal efficiency and with higher steam parameters (pressure and temperature) leads to increasing the attractiveness of replacing old recovery boiler types with modern recovery boilers. However, due to current low prices of EE the benefit from extra EE produced (compared to the system with old recovery boiler type) the attractiveness of purchasing modern recovery boiler instead of old type recovery boiler is not so significant for industry.

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